

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Islamic and conventional banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the CSR; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the CSR based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the CSR using a Library Research study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 317 journal publications regarding the CSR; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the CSR are divided into 8 clusters and 229 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Library Research studies, there are 4 main topics around the CSR. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics around CSR, so that future researchers can find out research gaps about CSR. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around CSR that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can be a reference for future researchers.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Initially, sharia banking activities were to expand banking services to the wider community who needed capital without an interest system (Lubis, 2022). Sharia banking has two roles, namely as a business entity and a social entity. As a social agency, Islamic banks have the obligation to manage, collect and distribute social funds (CSR) such as zakat, infaq and alms (Rumawi, 2021). The difference that exists in distributing funds to the public in conventional banks is that they use the principle of loss sharing, while Islamic banks use the principle of profit sharing. Source of funds for community welfare at Sharia Commercial Banks (BUS) comes from DPK (Third Party Funds), which consists of savings, current accounts, deposits and savings (Ananda & NR, 2020). These funds are deposited by the public which are managed by the bank and will be invested. Collecting TPF is a financing activity that will be allocated. Financing at Islamic banks is profit sharing (S. Astuti, 2019). The allocated CSR funds are also customer funds allocated to communities in need, for example business capital using profit sharing agreements (NT Astuti & Suharni, 2020; Awaliyah, 2018; Solihudin, 2017; Sawitri, 2017; Nurhayati, 2017).

In previous research, it was stated that CSR or third party funds have an influence on financing and implications for income at Islamic commercial banks in Indonesia in research on the influence of the inflation rate on third party funds (Charatunnisa, 2019). The research results show that third party funds have a positive and significant influence on financing, meaning that the higher the third

party funds, the higher the distribution of financing. The case study in this research uses the Bukopin sharia bank as an object (Rosiana, 2018). Scientific publications about CSR funds in sharia banking continue to increase every year based on searches via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) (Ruddin, 2018).

The aim of this research is to map research topics around CSR using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) Library Research studies to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics around CSR, so that future researchers can find out the gaps in research around CSR. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around CSR that are often or rarely studied by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

Literature Review

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is non-financial and financial information related to the social and physical fields through organizational relationships. CSR can also be recorded in separate social reports and company annual reports (Purwadi, 2016). Understanding CSR is divided into three important things, namely profit, people and planet. The 3P concept aims to enable companies, institutions or organizations to gain profits, but also to advance people and ensure a prosperous life on the planet (Yudiana, 2016). The Islamic view of CSR is the implementation of Maqasid al-syari'ah where business activities seek to create the benefit of society, not just pursuing profits. CSR activities in sharia banking are very close and influence the basis of sharia banking which is in accordance with Islamic teachings (Iqbal, 2017).

Bibliometric studies are the analysis of data displayed visually through mapping tools. This analysis is very helpful in mapping the research being carried out. Bibliometrics is also a tool used to evaluate the qualitative and quantitative research trends of a study over time. The methods used in bibliometric studies are literature databases and measuring characteristics of literature articles. Bibliometric applications are divided into two ways, namely bibliometric (performance) calculations which are indicators of different attitude levels and bibliometric network visualization and analysis. Meanwhile, bibliometric study parameters are divided into descriptive bibliometrics and evaluative bibliometrics (Dubyna et al., 2022). VOSviewer is a program computers used to create maps based on data networks and visualize the exploration of maps in the data. VOSviewer presents three visualizations, namely: network visualization, overlay visualization and density visualization (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library Research is a scientific method used as a technique in conducting research. Library Researchs are used by researchers as a method for identifying theories, such as identifying gaps between theories and relationships that occur in research. Library Research activities include collecting information or data, evaluating information, theories, research results, and data, as well as studying the results of publishing research articles, books, and matters related to research preparation (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library

Research studies. The research object is Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on CSR in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Corporate Social Responsibility " and "CSR" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals that have been published collected the data; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding CSR using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year;

(2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around CSR using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around CSR using Library Research studies (Budianto, 2023c) (Budianto, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rohimah et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023).

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications around Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 317 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2008 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal article data about CSR by year

Year Publicatio n	Amount Publication	Year Publication	Amount Publication	Year Publication	Amount Publication
2008	1	2014	17	2019	31
2009	1	2015	22	2020	30

2010	1	2016	23	2021	44
2011	2	2017	32	2022	46
2012	9	2018	37	2023	13
2013	8				

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Institutions or affiliates that often publish articles about CSR funds in sharia and conventional financial institutions are the Accounting Journal, Economic Journal, FEB Student Scientific Journal, and Accounting E-Journal.

Table 2. Data from institutions and journals that publish journal articles about CSR

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Amount
	Publication
Accounting journal	18
Economic Journal	13
FEB Student Scientific Journal	9
Accounting E-Journal	5
Diponegoro Journal of Accounting	4
Journal of Economics and Business	3
Economic Studies Bulletin, Indonesian Accounting Scientific Journal, Owner: Research and Accounting Journal, Mutiara Madani Accounting and Management Journal, Journal of Accounting and Tax, MALIA: Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance, Accounting Student Scientific Journal	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows the authors who wrote the most scientific articles about CSR funds in sharia and conventional financial institutions on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital).

Table 3. Researcher Productivity around CSR

Researcher	Amount
	Publication
Budiasih, I Gusti Ayu Nyoman (Udayana University Bali)	3
Astuti, Susi (PGRI Yogyakarta University)	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Mapping Research Topics around Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking using the VOSviewer Bibliometric Study

banking practice, IDX, impact, Indonesia stock exchange, Islamic commercial bank, Islamic corporate government, Islamic corporate social, negative effect, performance, period, population, quantitative research, research, risk, management, sampling, secondary data, significant effect, significant positive effect, square, stock exchange, sustainability report, type.

- Cluster 4, yellow covers 32 topics, namely: analysis, sharia commercial banks, BEI, Indonesian stock exchange, BUS, company age, corporate social responsibility, data, deposit ratio, board of commissioners, financing, firm size, good corporate governance, GRI, investors, managerial ownership, using purposive methods, analytical methods, registered banking, companies, banking companies, profitability, purposive sampling, public shares, sample, year, data analysis techniques, company value, volume.
- Cluster 5, purple covers 28 topics, namely: annual report, assets, asset ratio, CAR, coefficient, company, content analysis, corporate social responsibility, CSR variables, debt, equity, equity ratio, financial performance, firm value, GCG, hypothesis testing, insignificant effect, quantitative method, research sample. Return, ROA, ROE, significance, simultaneous effect, t test, test, total assets, total sample.
- Cluster 6, light blue covers 23 topics, namely: board, Indonesian stock exchange year, commissioner, company size, corporate value, CSR activity, director, disclosure, factor, GRI G4, IAH, implication, independent commissioner, indicator, influence, institutional ownership, investment account holder, leverage, liquidity, managerial ownership, number, score.
- Cluster 7, orange covers 21 topics, namely: analysis techniques, conventional banks with, bank sector, CSR disclosure, data collection, with, intellectual capital, market performance, multiple linear regression, observation, research aims, corporate disclosure, banking, positive effect, multiple linear regression, profitability, profitability, sample, technique, analysis technique.
- Cluster 8, brown covers 6 topics, namely: capital intensity, independent commissioner, Indonesian stock exchange, multiple regression analysis, tax aggressiveness.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking using a Library Research Study

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 12 CSR implementations in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, evaluate. The following are general steps that can be followed in the banking CSR evaluation process: (1) Determine banking CSR evaluation objectives; (2) Identifying performance indicators that can be used to measure the achievement of CSR goals; (3) Collect data related to CSR programs and activities carried out by banks; (4) Analyzing data to evaluate CSR program achievements; (5) Impact evaluation aims to assess whether the CSR program has achieved the stated objectives and provided the expected benefits; (6) Evaluation results need to be reported and communicated to relevant stakeholders; and (7) Evaluation of banking CSR must provide useful feedback for improving programs and activities in the future.

Second, policy law. The following are the general steps involved in implementing CSR by banks: (1) Banks will establish a CSR policy that includes the vision, mission and goals to be achieved through their CSR program; (2) Banks must identify social, environmental and economic issues that are relevant to their business and prioritize these issues based on the impact they may have; (3) Based on the results of identifying CSR issues, the bank will plan CSR programs in accordance with established policies; (4) Banks must determine an appropriate

budget for their CSR programs; (5) After planning CSR programs, the bank will implement these programs according to a predetermined schedule; (6) Banks must monitor and evaluate the implementation of their CSR programs to ensure the achievement of objectives and desired impacts; (7) Banks must regularly report their CSR activities to the authorities, shareholders and the general public; and (8) Banks are responsible for complying with applicable legal regulations and ethical standards in implementing their CSR.

Third, Go Online service at Bank Mandiri KC Surabaya. Go Online services at Bank Mandiri KC Surabaya refer to banking services provided through platforms. With this service, customers can access their accounts, carry out transactions and manage their finances via the internet. In the context of CSR funds, Bank Mandiri KC Surabaya can use part of their CSR funds to support the development of Go Online services. This may include investing in technology infrastructure, developing online banking applications, improving data security and privacy, and providing adequate customer support for Go Online services. The benefit of implementing the Go Online service for CSR funds is that it increases accessibility and comfort for customers in managing their finances. Customers can carry out banking transactions anytime and anywhere via devices connected to the internet. This can also help reduce the time and costs associated with physically visiting a bank branch.

Fourth, communication model. There are several common steps and components in implementing the CSR communication model in banking. The following are several things that are usually done: (1) The first step in implementing the CSR communication model is to determine the goals and vision that the bank wants to achieve in implementing CSR activities; (2) Once the CSR objectives are determined, the bank needs to identify the beneficiaries of the CSR program; (3) Banks need to determine the amount of funds to be allocated for CSR programs as well as other resources needed, such as workforce, time and facilities; (4) Banks need to develop effective communication strategies to promote and inform CSR activities to various stakeholders; (5) Once a communication strategy has been developed, the bank can start implementing CSR communication activities; and (6) After implementing CSR communication, banks need to evaluate and monitor the effectiveness of the CSR program and the communication strategies used.

Fifth, stakeholder perceptions. The following are some general perceptions that stakeholders may have regarding CSR funds in banking: (1) Customers may view CSR funds as banking efforts to make positive contributions to society and the environment; (2) Shareholders can view CSR funds as additional expenditure that can affect company profits; (3) Employees may feel proud to work for a company that has strong CSR initiatives; (4) The public in general can have a positive perception of banking CSR funds if they see concrete benefits from these programs; and (5) Governments and regulators may expect banks to comply with regulations governing the management of CSR funds.

Sixth, CSR implementation at BNI, BRI Porong Unit Office, Bank Nagari KC Pangkalan, BPRS Bhakti Sumekar KC Pamekasan, BRI KC Wonosari, BPTN KC Ciliwung Surabaya, BPD Central Kalimantan, Bank Sumut Syariah KC Padangsidempuan. There are several general steps taken in implementing banking CSR. The following are several stages that are usually carried out: (1) The bank identifies and sets CSR priorities based on business objectives, company values, and the desired impact on society and the surrounding environment; (2) After identifying priorities, the bank will develop a detailed strategy to implement the CSR program; (2) The Bank consults with stakeholders, such as government, NGOs and local communities, to understand their needs and expectations; (3) The Bank implements established CSR programs; (4) After the CSR program is implemented, the bank will

carry out monitoring and evaluation to measure its impact and effectiveness; And (5) The Bank reports CSR activities and achievements to the public and stakeholders.

Seventh, use of funds. The following are some examples of the use of CSR funds in banking: (1) Many banks use CSR funds to support education, such as providing scholarships to outstanding students from underprivileged families, building or repairing educational facilities, providing equipment and textbooks, and holding training programs and development for teachers; (2) CSR funds are also often used to support the health sector; (3) Banks can use CSR funds to reduce negative impacts on the environment; (4) Funds CSR can also be allocated to strengthen and develop communities around banking; (5) Banks can also use CSR funds to help address relevant social issues.

Eighth, increase Inclusive Business. The following are several ways in which increasing Inclusive Business can contribute to the use of CSR funds by banks: (1) Banks can use their CSR funds to form partnerships with inclusive business actors, such as small farmer groups or less developed local producer groups; (2) Banks can use their CSR funds to provide entrepreneurship training, financial training, or capital assistance to low-income communities; (3) Banks can use their CSR funds to provide micro and small financing to underprivileged community groups; (4) Banks can use CSR funds to organize financial literacy programs aimed at underserved communities; and (5) Banking can encourage innovation in the use of CSR funds by developing inclusive financial products and services that are more suited to the needs of underprivileged groups in society.

Ninth, improving the welfare of farmers and village businesses. This can be done in the following ways: (1) Banks can use CSR funds to provide training and education to farmers and village business owners; (2) Banking can provide access to financing and working capital to farmers and village businesses through CSR funds; (3) Banks can use CSR funds to help farmers and village businesses develop their markets and improve marketing capabilities; (4) Banking can support the development of agricultural infrastructure and technology through CSR funds; and (5) Banks can use CSR funds to support the formation of farmer cooperatives and collaboration networks between village businesses.

Tenth, Bank Indonesia scholarship and teaching program. The following is general information regarding Bank Indonesia scholarship and teaching programs funded through CSR funds in banking: (1) Bank Indonesia Scholarships. The Bank Indonesia scholarship program is aimed at supporting outstanding and potential students who need financial assistance to complete their studies. This scholarship is open to undergraduate (S1) and postgraduate (S2) students in various disciplines related to economics, banking, finance and other related sectors. Prospective scholarship recipients must go through a strict selection, including an administrative process, written test, interview, and academic achievement assessment. Scholarship recipients will receive tuition fees, living assistance and the opportunity to take part in an internship program at Bank Indonesia. (2) Bank Indonesia Teaching Program. Bank Indonesia's teaching program aims to strengthen the quality of economic education in Indonesia through collaboration with universities and educational institutions. In this program, lecturers and teaching staff from Bank Indonesia teach at partner universities to share their knowledge and experience in the fields of economics, banking and finance. Bank Indonesia collaborates with various universities and educational institutions to design teaching programs that are relevant to the needs of the banking and financial industry. This teaching program can include classroom teaching, curriculum preparation, lecturer training, and research and development activities.

Eleventh, representation of CSR-based banking literacy park. The following are several ways such representation can be carried out: (1) CSR funds can be used to establish a banking literacy park that provides free access to various books, magazines, brochures and educational materials related to banking; (2) CSR funds

can be allocated to organize training programs and workshops regarding financial and banking literacy; (3) CSR funds can be used to mass produce and distribute educational materials about banking; (4) CSR funds can be allocated for developing mobile applications or digital platforms that provide banking-related information and resources; and (5) Banks can use CSR funds to collaborate with schools and local communities in holding banking literacy activities.

Twelfth, social and environmental responsibility. The following are several important aspects related to social and environmental responsibility in managing CSR funds in banking: (1) Banks must transparently manage CSR funds and communicate the use of these funds to the public; (2) Banks must consider the environmental impact of their operations; (3) Banks must pay attention to the social welfare of customers, employees and local communities where they operate; (4) Banks must carry out their operations with high business ethics; and (5) Banks must interact with stakeholders, such as customers, employees, government and civil society, to understand their needs and expectations regarding social and environmental responsibility.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Measurement Methods in Sharia and Conventional Banking using Library Research

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 3 methods of measuring CSR in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, the General Report Initiative Index. The following are general steps that can be followed in using the GRI Index to measure CSR in the banking industry:

(1) Understanding the GRI Index: Understand the GRI Index well. GRI is an international framework used to measure, report and disclose a company's social, environmental and economic impact. Banks usually use GRI Standards in their CSR reporting. (2) Identify relevant CSR material: Identify the CSR issues that are most relevant in the banking context. For example, implementing sustainability practices, consumer protection, financial inclusion, environmental responsibility, and risk management related to banking activities. (3) Build a reporting framework: Create a reporting framework based on the GRI Index by referring to categories and indicators relevant to the banking industry. The GRI Index has four main categories: Economy, Environment, Human Rights, and Society.

(4) Data collection: Collect the data needed to fill in the indicators in each GRI category. This may involve internal data recording, research, or consultation with relevant departments within the banking organization. (5) Compile a CSR report: Use the data collected to compile a CSR report that includes information about banking practices relevant to the GRI categories. Ensure reports include sufficient, accurate, relevant and measurable information. (6) Report verification: To increase the credibility of your CSR report, consider conducting external verification by a third party. This verification can be carried out by an independent certification body that will check the sustainability of CSR reports based on the GRI Index framework. (7) Publish CSR report: Once the CSR report is verified, publish the report widely. This can be done through the company website, annual report, or a recognized CSR reporting platform.

Second, Triple Bottom Line /TBL. The following are general steps that can be used in implementing the CSR measurement method using TBL in the banking context: (1) Identify Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): Determine the relevant indicators for each TBL dimension. For example, for the financial dimension, the KPIs may include net profit, return on equity, or asset growth. For the social dimension, the KPIs can focus on philanthropic activities, employee volunteer activities, or customer satisfaction levels. For the environmental dimension, the KPIs may include reducing carbon emissions, using renewable energy, or waste

management. (2) Data Collection: Collect the data necessary to measure company performance in each TBL dimension. Data can come from financial reports, sustainability reports, employee surveys, market research, and other relevant data sources. (3) Performance Analysis: Evaluation of company performance in each TBL dimension using predetermined KPIs. Identify performance trends from time to time and compare it with the targets that have been set. (4) Reporting and Communication: Convey the results of company performance evaluations to stakeholders, such as shareholders, employees, customers and the general public. Use sustainability reports and annual reports to convey information about CSR initiatives, social and environmental impacts, and financial achievements. (5) Continuous Improvement: Based on the evaluation results, identify areas that need improvement and determine the actions to be taken to improve the company's performance in each TBL dimension. Support continuous improvement efforts through internal policies, training, investment and stakeholder engagement.

Third, Shariah Enterprise Theory. The following are general steps that can be used to measure CSR in banking using Shariah Enterprise Theory: (1) Identification of Sharia Principles: The first step is to identify the sharia principles that banking institutions must comply with. These principles include the prohibition of usury (interest), the prohibition of investment in sectors considered haram (such as alcohol, tobacco, gambling), as well as the principles of justice and sustainability. (2) Sharia Compliance Assessment: Carry out an assessment to assess the extent to which the bank complies with sharia principles in its operational activities. This assessment may involve an internal or external audit conducted by a sharia expert. (3) Identifying CSR Aspects: Identify CSR aspects that are relevant to the banking industry, such as support for education, the environment, health, poverty and community empowerment. (4) Development of Measurement Criteria: Based on sharia principles and CSR aspects that have been identified, create clear and measurable measurement criteria for each CSR aspect. For example, if education is a relevant aspect of CSR, measurement criteria could include the number of students receiving scholarships or educational development programs conducted by the bank. (5) Data Collection: Collect the data needed to measure CSR performance based on predetermined criteria. Data can include CSR activities and programs carried out by banks, the resulting impacts, and other related information. (6) Analysis and Evaluation: Analysis of collected data to evaluate the bank's CSR performance based on predetermined criteria. Identify strengths and weaknesses, as well as areas of improvement that may be needed. (7) Reporting and Transparency: Use evaluation results to create CSR reports that are transparent and easy to understand by stakeholders. Ensure that this report includes information about the CSR activities carried out by the bank, the resulting impact, as well as steps taken to improve CSR performance in the future.

Mapping Research Topics around the Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) on Sharia and Conventional Banking using Library Research

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 35 influences that CSR had on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, tax aggressiveness. With CSR, banks tend to pay more attention to social and environmental responsibility. This could have an impact on banking attitudes regarding tax practices. Banks that are committed to CSR are usually more likely to avoid aggressive tax practices, such as using legal loopholes to reduce tax liabilities. They may be inclined towards higher tax compliance as part of their social responsibility.

Second, brand equity. CSR can make a significant contribution to increasing banking brand equity. Through effective and measurable CSR programs, banks can

build better relationships with the community and consumers. Thus, banking reputation increases and this can influence consumer perceptions of quality, reliability and responsibility banking. Strong brand equity can have a positive impact on consumer trust, loyalty and banking decisions.

Third, brand image. CSR can also influence banking brand image. When banks are involved in CSR activities that are beneficial and in line with the values they uphold, they can build an image as companies that care about society and the environment. This can enhance the positive image of banks and portray them as socially responsible entities. In the long term, this can improve public perception of the bank and differentiate it from competitors.

Fourth, the bank's image. In the context of a bank's image, CSR can have a significant impact. Through good and sustainable CSR programs, banks can improve their reputation as institutions that play an active role in improving social welfare. By carrying out activities that include the environment, education, health or other community activities, banks can create a positive image as partners who help build a better society. This can increase public trust in banking and create better relationships with stakeholders.

Fifth, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR. Strong CSR practices in the banking industry can have a positive impact on CAR. This is due to several factors such as a good reputation, improved asset quality, and better relations with regulators and stakeholders. By implementing CSR, banks can gain public trust and reduce reputation risks that can affect CAR.

Sixth, corporate image. CSR can significantly influence the image of a company or bank. If a bank has a strong CSR program and focuses on relevant social and environmental issues, this can improve the company's image in the eyes of the public. Banks that are considered socially responsible and contribute to society will usually be rated better by potential customers, stakeholders and the general public. A positive company image can increase customer trust and loyalty and support long-term business growth.

Seventh, Corporate Financial Performance. Effective CSR implementation can have a positive impact on a company's financial performance. Although there is a view that CSR activities can reduce profitability, several studies show a positive relationship between CSR and CFP. This can happen because good CSR implementation can increase operational efficiency, reduce reputational and legal risks, and improve relationships with customers, employees and other stakeholders. In the long term, CSR can provide significant added value to companies through improving financial performance.

Eighth, Earnings Response Coefficient. ERC measures how much the market reacts to company earnings information. Studies on the influence of CSR on ERC are still limited, but several studies show a positive relationship between CSR and ERC. This shows that companies that implement CSR well can get better market support and a more positive response from investors. Transparent and effective disclosure of CSR information can reflect good management and strong business ethics, which can improve investor and market perceptions of the company.

Ninth, share prices. In the long term, effective implementation of CSR programs can have a positive influence on banking share prices. When banks have a good reputation in terms of social and environmental responsibility, this can increase investor confidence and their interest in investing in the company. Investors often tend to choose companies that are committed to responsible business practices, including CSR. With increasing demand for banking shares, share prices can increase as market confidence increases.

Tenth, social characteristics of the bank. CSR can influence a bank's social characteristics or banking identity as an institution that cares about social interests.

By involving themselves in CSR programs that are relevant to the social problems faced by society, banks can strengthen their image as responsible partners and help improve social conditions. This may include support for education, poverty alleviation programs, environmental protection, or other social activities. In this way, banking can build positive social characteristics and make a real contribution to society.

Eleventh, customer satisfaction. Good CSR implementation can have a positive impact on customer satisfaction. When banks engage in relevant and beneficial CSR activities, this can improve their image and reputation in the eyes of customers. Customers tend to prefer banks that are committed to social and environmental responsibility. In some cases, banks may also provide products or services that are directly related to CSR programs, such as financing for environmental or community development projects. This can increase customer satisfaction and strengthen the relationship between customers and banks.

Twelfth, job satisfaction. CSR can have a positive influence on job satisfaction among banking employees. When banks are involved in CSR programs, this provides an opportunity for employees to be involved in activities that provide social and environmental benefits. This can increase employees' sense of pride and motivation, because they feel they work for a company that cares about relevant social issues. CSR programs can also reflect a company's values and provide deeper meaning to their work. As a result, employee job satisfaction can increase, which in turn can have a positive impact on their performance and productivity.

Thirteenth, business sustainability/ Going Concern. CSR can have a positive influence on the sustainability of banking businesses. By involving themselves in CSR activities, banks can build a positive image in the eyes of the public, strengthen relationships with customers and business partners, and increase public trust. This can help banks to maintain their business in the long term and achieve business sustainability.

Fourteenth, the decision to save. CSR can also influence people's saving decisions. If a bank is actively involved in social activities that benefit society, consumers tend to be more inclined to save or invest in that bank. Bank involvement in CSR can also reflect values valued by consumers, such as transparency, sustainability and social responsibility. This can increase consumer confidence and make them more likely to choose the bank as a place to store and manage their funds.

Fifteenth, market performance. Effective CSR practices can improve banking market performance. When a bank has a good reputation in terms of social and environmental responsibility, this can influence investors' and market analysts' perceptions of the company. Investors and analysts tend to give more value to companies that are considered socially and environmentally responsible. Thus, banks that are active in CSR can attract the interest of potential investors, increase stock liquidity, and strengthen their market performance.

Sixteenth, company performance. Good CSR implementation can have a positive impact on overall company performance. Involving yourself in CSR activities can improve the company's image in the eyes of the public, strengthen relationships with customers and business partners, and increase employee satisfaction. All of this can contribute to improving a company's reputation and competitive advantage. In addition, through CSR, companies can build better relationships with the government, community and non-governmental organizations, which can support the company's overall growth and development.

Seventeenth, employee performance. Effective CSR implementation can improve employee performance. When companies demonstrate their commitment to social and environmental responsibility, this can have a positive impact on employee motivation and satisfaction. Employees who feel proud to work for a company that

those who have a strong CSR program tend to be more passionate, loyal, and motivated to give their best in their work.

Eighteenth, organizational/employee commitment. CSR can contribute to increasing organizational and employee commitment. With a CSR program that is integrated with company values, employees feel more connected and committed to the company's goals and vision. They feel that their company has a positive impact on society and the environment, which in turn increases their loyalty and pride in the organization.

Nineteenth, bank profits. CSR can have an influence on bank profits. Although it may not be immediately visible in the short term, good CSR implementation can create long-term benefits for the company. By implementing socially and environmentally responsible business practices, companies can build a strong reputation, enhance their brand image, and expand their customer base. This can have a positive impact on long-term bank profits through increased sales, competitive advantage and access to new business opportunities.

Twentieth, brand loyalty. CSR can contribute to brand loyalty. When companies demonstrate their commitment to social and environmental responsibility, consumers tend to have more positive perceptions of the brand. Customers who are aware of corporate social responsibility will be more likely to choose products or services from companies that have strong CSR programs. Thus, effective CSR implementation can increase brand loyalty, retain existing customers, and attract new customers.

Twenty-one, customer loyalty. CSR can have a positive influence on customer loyalty. When banks involve themselves in social and environmental activities that are beneficial to society, this can create a positive image in the eyes of customers. Customers are more likely to remain loyal and maintain relationships with banks they perceive as socially responsible. In addition, transparent and open CSR efforts can build trust and increase customer loyalty.

Twenty-second, company value. Effective CSR implementation can contribute to increasing company value. By investing in activities that support society and the environment, companies can build a strong reputation and gain the trust of stakeholders. A company's value can increase due to attention to social and environmental issues, which are increasingly important in the view of many investors and consumers today.

Twenty-third, Non Performing Loans /NPL. Although the direct relationship between CSR and Non-Performing Loans (NPL) is not very clear, good CSR implementation can indirectly help reduce NPL risk. When banks are actively involved in positive social and economic efforts, for example by providing financial training to the community or supporting entrepreneurship programs, this can increase financial literacy and economic stability in the surrounding environment. In the long term, these efforts can contribute to reducing NPL risk because people who are more financially educated tend to have higher levels of financial success.

Twenty-fourth, bank income. Implementing CSR can have a positive impact on bank revenues. When banks invest in social or environmental projects that are relevant to their business, this can improve their image in the eyes of customers and the general public. This positive image can help in acquiring new customers, retaining existing customers, and increasing customer loyalty. In addition, a better relationship between banks and the community can open up new opportunities for business and growth, such as support for partnership programs with local business actors which have the potential to increase bank revenues.

Twenty-fifth, community empowerment. In the context of CSR, community empowerment is one of the main focuses. Through CSR activities, banking can contribute to improving society's capabilities in terms of the economy, education, health and others. For example, banks can organize training programs

finance and entrepreneurship for the community, providing access to inclusive financial services, and supporting community development programs. This helps improve people's quality of life and independence, as well as creating long-term positive impacts.

Twenty-sixth, poverty alleviation. CSR can play an important role in poverty alleviation efforts. Banks that are committed to CSR often involve themselves in social programs aimed at reducing economic disparities and providing opportunities for those less fortunate. For example, banks can provide microloans to small and medium entrepreneurs, organize financial inclusion programs for the poor, or allocate part of their profits to poverty alleviation programs. This helps create economic equality and improve social welfare.

Twenty-seventh, customer perception. CSR can influence customer perceptions of banks or financial institutions. Customers tend to provide added value to companies that are committed to social responsibility. When banks engage in CSR activities that are seen as positive, such as supporting education, the environment, or public health, this can increase customer trust and loyalty. Customers can also feel proud and have an emotional bond with banks that are committed to CSR, which in turn can influence their decisions in choosing and using banking services.

Twenty-eighth, company brand preferences. CSR can also impact a company's brand preferences. Consumers tend to prefer brands or companies that have a good reputation in terms of social responsibility. If banks carry out CSR activities transparently and effectively, this can improve brand image and create consumer trust. Consumers also tend to feel more emotionally connected to brands that care about social and environmental issues. Over time, strong brand preferences can help companies retain loyal customers and attract new customers.

Twenty-ninth, company reputation. CSR can have a positive impact on the reputation of banking companies. Through effective and transparent CSR implementation, companies can gain trust and respect from the community. People tend to prefer dealing with companies that care about social and environmental issues, so that the company's reputation can increase.

Thirtieth, Return On Assets /ROA. CSR can influence banking company ROA. By involving themselves in positive social and environmental activities, companies can improve their image in the eyes of society and stakeholders. This can have a positive impact on customer loyalty, acceptance of the company's products and services, and ultimately increase revenue and ROA.

Thirty-one, Return On Equity /ROE. CSR can also affect the ROE of banking companies. By implementing good CSR activities, companies can build better relationships with the community and stakeholders. This can create new business opportunities, increase customer satisfaction and reduce reputational risks. In the long term, this can increase company profits and ROE.

Thirty-second, Repurchase Intention. CSR can influence Repurchase Intention or the intention to repurchase products or use company services. When banking companies are active in positive CSR activities, this can build customer loyalty. Customers tend to choose to return to transactions with companies that are considered socially and environmentally responsible. Thus, CSR can increase Repurchase Intention and support long-term business growth.

Thirty-third, bank risk. CSR can have a positive impact on bank risk management. Through CSR activities, banks can strengthen their reputation, build good relationships with stakeholders, and reduce reputational risks

can be detrimental to their business activities. For example, banks committed to CSR can adopt socially and environmentally responsible business practices, such as limiting investment in controversial or high-risk industries. This can help banks reduce credit, reputation and operational risks.

Thirty-fourth, tax avoidance. In the context of tax avoidance, the influence of CSR on banking can vary. Some banking companies can use CSR practices to improve their image in terms of tax compliance and social responsibility. However, on the other hand, there is also the possibility that CSR practices can be used as a strategy to obtain tax benefits or exploit loopholes in tax regulations. Therefore, the influence of CSR on tax avoidance will depend greatly on how banking companies implement and report their CSR practices, as well as on the tax regulations in force in that country.

Thirty-fifth, stock trading volume. The relationship between CSR and stock trading volume is not direct. However, in the long term, consistent and transparent CSR activities can influence investors' perceptions of banking companies. Investors who consider social and environmental factors in their investment decisions tend to be more interested in companies that are committed to social responsibility. This can influence investors' perceptions of the company's value and, in turn, can impact share trading volume. However, it is important to remember that stock trading volume is also influenced by other factors such as financial performance, market conditions, and overall investor sentiment.

Mapping Research Topics around Factors that Influence Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Disclosure in Sharia and Conventional Banking using Library Research

Based on a Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 45 factors that influence CSR disclosure in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: (1) Islamic accounting; (2) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR; (3) Corporate Financial Performance; (4) Covid-19; (5) National diversity of directors; (6) Earnings management; (7) Islamic business ethics; (8) Corporate Governance Elements; (9) Financing Deposit Ratio /FDR; (10) Gender of directors; (11) Good Corporate Governance /GCG; (12) Green Accounting; (13) Islamic Social Reporting /ISR Index; (14) Intellectual Capital; (15) Islamic Work Ethics /IWE; (16) Islamic Corporate Governance; (17) Islamic Governance Score /IG- Score; (18) Investment Account Holder /IAH; (19) Number of members of the Supervisory Board Sharia/DPS; (20) Number of Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS meetings; (21) Number of board of commissioners; (22) Cash; (23) Company characteristics; (24) Audit committee characteristics; (25) Public share ownership; (26) Institutional ownership; (27) Managerial ownership; (28) Annual financial report; (29) Leverage; (30) Maqashid Al-Syariah; (31) Company value; (32) Non Performing Financing /NPF; (33) Financing; (34) Bank growth; (35) Profitability (36) Return On Assets /ROA; (37) Return On Equity /ROE); (37) Business strategy; (38) Liquidity ratio; (39) Solvency ratio; (40) Company reputation; (41) Corporate governance; (42) Industry type; (43) Bank soundness level; (44) Bank size; AND (45) Age of company.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period of From 2008 to 2023, originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there were 317 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the results of network visualization around CSR in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into

8 clusters and 229 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 54 topics, cluster 2 consists of 33 topics, cluster 3 consists of 32 topics, cluster 4 consists of 32 topics, cluster 5 consists of 28 topics, cluster 6 consists of 23 topics, cluster 7 consists of 21 topics, and cluster 8 consists of 6 topics. Third, based on mapping Library Research studies, there are 12 topics related to CSR implementation, 3 CSR measurement methods, 35 influences caused by CSR, and 45 factors that influence CSR disclosure in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

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